

1 AIRE expression on the outer surface of the solid tumor describes an active immune evasion process in
2 cancer.

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7 We measured total transcription in the tumor core and the tumor surface in a CNS solid tumor model *in*
8 *vivo* to describe the 3-dimensional composition of the solid tumor in humans. We describe here the
9 presence of an active immune evasion mechanism in human cancer based at least in part on tailored
10 expression of AIRE on the outer surface of the solid tumor. The data indicated the capacity of a tumor to
11 intently design its structure to limit immune surveillance by the host.

12 Citations

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